

University Marine Energy Research Community

2023 Conference

4-6 October | Durham, NH, USA

Point-absorber survivability analysis with collaborative CFD

Kate Macolini^a, Alan McCall^a, Dr. Chris Chartrand^b, Dr. Nhu Nguyen^b

^aDehlsen Associates, LLC, 101 E. Victoria St., Suite F, Santa Barbara, CA 93101, United States

^bSandia National Laboratories, Albuquerque, NM, United States

Abstract

Dehlsen Associates, LLC (DA) is currently developing a preliminary design of its C1P6 wave energy device. The C1P6 is a floating point-absorber with a direct-drive high performance linear generator. This presentation will explore preliminary analysis of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) on a scaled C1P6 model under extreme sea states conducted by Sandia National Laboratories (SNL) in partnership with DA. Two simulated cases will be validated through wave tank testing at the University of New Hampshire (UNH). The DA team conducted wave tank testing at UNH in May with help from the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL). A 1:20th scale model of the C1P6 was tested under several sets of regular wave conditions. Force predictions from the opensource CFD tool, OpenFOAM, will be validated by wave tank testing results. Simulations will be completed by SNL and followed closely by DA for comparison and analysis with experimental data. Validation of mooring tensions, power take off forces, and six degrees of freedom motion may be detailed from this joint effort. The validated numerical model will be further utilized to quantify extreme sea states and analyze device survivability in extreme conditions.

Keywords: point-absorber, survivability, validation, CFD, experimental testing, motion tracking

1. Introduction

The C1P6 is a floating two-body point-absorber with a direct-drive high performance linear generator developed by Centipod Wave Energy, a subsidiary technology of Dehlsen Associates, LLC based in Santa Barbara, California. The two bodies and the points of interest for loads analysis are identified in Figure 1. The DA team conducted 1:20th scale experimental testing in May at the UNH campus wave tank with assistance from an NREL representative. Mooring tensions, power take off forces, and six DOF kinematics were collected using a combination of available sensors and innovative adaptations. Data were recorded for sets of operational and extreme sea states, from which two sets of extreme sea state data will be used to validate OpenFOAM [1] predicted values compiled by SNL partners. Most recently, DA provided post-processed data and updated inputs to SNL members for model refinement.

Nomenclature

CFD computational fluid dynamics
DOF degrees of freedom

Fig. 1. CIP6 device geometry and points of interest for loads analysis

2. Methodology

Data were recorded for wave tank testing of eight operational sea states and two extreme sea states. The scaled extreme sea state data from the waves defined in Table 1 will be compared with OpenFOAM [1] predictions from simulations conducted by SNL partners. Table parameter T_e refers to the energy period and EWH refers to the extreme wave height. These waves are represented in Figure 2 by the markers labeled “EWH-adj(m)”.

Table 1. Tank adjusted extreme sea states (TESS)

	TESS-01	TESS-02
T_e (s)	1.3	1.8
EWH (m)	0.26	0.33

Fig. 2. Tank ESS wave height adjustment

Mooring tensions were captured with load cells and wave dynamics were characterized with probes developed by a DA team member. Video documentation was enabled by the opensource software OBS Studio [2] activated with an in-house automation script. Motion tracking data were extracted from these videos using the opensource software Kinovea [3]. An example of Kinovea motion tracking [3] is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Kinovea motion tracking of C1P6 under operational sea states

Data collected during wave tank testing at UNH were post-processed by DA team members with calculations embedded in in-house automated Python scripts. Post-processing of raw data has concluded, and SNL partners have been updated as they develop CFD simulations concurrently.

3. Results

Experimental testing concluded at the end of May, and DA data post-processing extended into the beginning of August. Consequently, SNL contributions and comparison with DA data are still in progress.

Initial review of operational sea state kinematic data shows the largest axial load occurring in heave followed by surge. The upper and lower housing of the C1P6 experience similar load patterns with the lower housing generally seeing a lower magnitude load. Bending moments occur primarily in pitch.

Completion of analysis will help DA optimize design parameters and numerically quantify extreme loads.

4. Conclusions

Preliminary conclusions regarding CFD validation using experimental data are forthcoming. In addition to the completion of the initial scope, DA hopes to test a wider range of wave conditions. Validation of CFD will also be

cross-verified with other software. This work is enabled by professional partnerships with UNH, SNL, and NREL; DOE funding through award DE-EE0009956; and a small but mighty group of positive thinkers.

Acknowledgements

I would like to acknowledge Centipod Wave Energy Managing Director Alan McCall for his direction and support during wave tank testing and data post-processing. I would also like to thank Dr. Nhu Nguyen and Dr. Chris Chartrand of SNL for their CFD simulation efforts, general guidance, and willingness to contribute to this presentation.

References

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